

DYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF ADHESIVELY BONDED SINGLE LAP JOINTS USING FULL-FIELD MEASUREMENT TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

Digital Image Correlation (DIC) is used to provide full-field analysis of the strains generated within an adhesively bonded composite single lap joint. Testing is conducted both quasi-statically at 2 mm/min and an intermediate strain rate, focusing on the root of the discontinuity between adherends where failure initiation is observed. The intermediate rate loading is applied using an Instron VHS 80/20 servo hydraulic test machine operated at 2.5 m/s. High speed cameras are used to capture images at frame rates of 25 kHz. These are used in the DIC to provide the axial, peel and shear strain distributions at the root of the discontinuity between adherends, hence identifying the mechanisms for damage initiation and growth.

A significant strengthening effect was observed in the high rate loading; increasing the failure load from 4.5 kN to 9.7 kN. This increase indicates possible viscoelastic strengthening of the epoxy matrix in the matrix dominated through-thickness direction, resisting the high peel stresses generated around the geometric discontinuity. Damage initiation is observed to occur at approximately 50% of the failure load for both quasi static and high strain rate loading conditions. The strains evaluated prior to initiation are observed to be very similar for both cases, indicating that the generation of cracks at the root of the discontinuity is not strain rate dependent. The failure surfaces of the specimens loaded quasi statically and at high rate are markedly different, indicating a strengthening effect from the CSM face sheet material, producing crack blunting and fibre bridging, limiting damage until a critical strain is reached and ultimate failure occurs.

1 INTRODUCTION

Joints present a significant design challenge to engineers as they inherently contain discontinuities in both geometry and material properties, generating complex stress and strain distributions. Mechanical fastenings such as rivets, screws and bolts are common joining approaches used in industry [1]–[3]. The main alternative to mechanical fastening is adhesive bonding, whereby the adhesive between adherends constitutes a structural layer formed by chemically bonding the adherend surfaces, to facilitate load transfer. The use of adhesive bonding provides a significant reduction in joint weight compared to mechanical fasteners [4], increasing the structural efficiency. Bonded composite joints provide a challenge as laminated composites material are strong in the direction of the fibres but are weak normal to the fibre direction, where their strength is dominated by the mechanical properties of the brittle polymer matrix. Their weak through-thickness properties, and the relatively high localised through-thickness direct stresses (i.e. peel stresses) at the root of the discontinuity, make the laminated adherend susceptible to the initiation of interlaminar cracks, which may leading to joint failure.

Previous work by the authors [5][6] has used Digital Image Correlation (DIC) [7] to evaluate the individual strain components generated within the joint up to and including failure. Strain fields were examined at the root of the discontinuity in the joint to provide detailed, data-rich, measurement of the developing strain fields. Under high-rate loading composite materials display rate-dependent material

properties, such as increasing strength due to viscoelastic effects within the matrix [8]. Investigation of joints under dynamic loading has also observed changes in the response of the adhesive used within the bonded joints [9]–[11] as well as the overall strength of bonded assemblies in tension [12], [13], compression [14] and shear [15], [16]. In the present paper high speed cameras are used to capture images for DIC, which provides the strain fields developed within the joint structure when loaded dynamically. Changes in the joint strength and strain distribution are identified and compared with quasi static test results.

2 JOINT STRUCTURE

A single lap joint was constructed from four layers of 800g/m^2 unidirectional and 14 layers of 450g/m^2 chopped strand mat (CSM) glass fibre in a $[\text{CSM}_7 90_4 \text{CSM}_7]$ layup using Gurit Prime 20 LV epoxy resin and the resin infusion process. The joint specimen is shown Fig 1a); it is 25 mm wide with an adherend overlap length of 25 mm. The adherends had a total length of 150 mm with a 50 mm tapered end tab design. Araldite 2015, a toughened structural epoxy adhesive, was used to bond the adherends together. The joint assembly was post cured at 80°C for 1 hour. The layup and overlap length of the joint was designed to ensure that the response in the through-thickness direction was adequately captured using the optics and cameras available. Adhesive spew fillets were removed during construction to artificially increase the peel strain in the thick, stiff adherends. The layup selected had thick layers of dissimilar material to provide sufficient thickness across each material layer for a large number of data points to be captured for the DIC. An image of the layered joint structure is shown in Fig 1b).

Figure 1: Single lap joint a) Schematic b) Image of the layered composite structure in joint

3 QUASI-STATIC ANALYSIS

To evaluate the influence of the localized strain distributions during the onset of failure, high speed imaging was used to capture the fast initiation and development of damage within the joint. Six joints were tested quasi-statically in an Instron 5569 electromechanical test machine and loaded at 2 mm/min up to failure. Images were recorded at 1000 Hz with a 10 bit Photron SA5 high speed camera with an image resolution of 464×384 pixels. Magnifying optics were used, increasing the spatial resolution but

at the expense of reducing the size of the area of interest for the analysis. A sigma 105 mm macro lens was attached to the Photron SA5 producing an image resolution of 75 pixels / mm. An area of interest 6.2 mm x 5.1 mm was imaged at the root of the discontinuity between the adherends. Illumination was provided by a LED ring flash light mounted onto the lens, delivering consistent cold lighting of the specimen. The stochastic speckle pattern, which the correlation algorithm uses to calculate deformation vectors, was applied using RS components matt black aerosol, fitted with a needle cap, onto a white background painted onto the specimen. The pattern properties were matched to the resolution of the image [17], minimising errors in the correlation. The image sequence was analysed using the LaVision Davis 8.0 correlation software with a subset size of 69 x 69 pixels and step size of 20 pixels, producing a spatial resolution of approximately 4 data points / mm. Similar experimental methods have been used to analyse small areas of interest around the root of the discontinuity between adherends in a double butt strap joint with high confidence [5].

Fig 2 shows the a) axial, b) shear and c) peel strain distributions within the joint at 2.7 kN. Fig 2a) shows higher axial strain in the constrained adherend on the right compared to the free adherend on the left, identifying the free adherend to be lightly loaded. The axial strain field provides a quantitative visualisation of the differential extension between adherends in the single lap joint due to the different boundary conditions within the free end of the adherend on the left and the highly loaded adherend on the right. Fig 2b) shows that the shear strains are greatest within the adhesive layer between adherends at the discontinuity, decreasing rapidly away from the adhesive into the surrounding CSM material. Peel strains, shown in Fig 2c), are concentrated in the left hand adherend close to the free end, where load eccentricity is at its greatest, reducing rapidly away from the discontinuity.

Fig 3 shows data for an increased load of 3.1 kN; here the peel and shear strain distributions develop into distinct, yet inter-dependent features. Analysis of the shear strains identifies a non-uniform distribution across the thickness of the adhesive layer, generating higher shear strains closer to the interface between the adhesive and the adherend on the left, propagating into the CSM face sheets, Fig 6b). The peel strain in Fig 3c) is greatest adjacent to the region of high shear strain at the interface between the adhesive and left hand adherend. The position of these concentrations indicates a coupling between the through-thickness and shear material responses at the interface resulting from the load transfer across the adhesive into the adherend. A similar localisation of the strains along the interface was observed by Ruiz [18] using high magnification Moiré interferometry. The high strain along the interface is suspected to feature heavily in the initiation and propagation of damage.

The first visual signs of damage in the joint can be observed at 3.1 kN in the raw images. A very small 0.13 mm crack forms at the root of the discontinuity at the interface between the adhesive and the right hand, constrained, adherend. As this crack is very small it is not easily discerned in the images. For the purpose of illustration, Figure 4a) shows the crack at 3.8 kN when it is more clearly visible in the image. Shear strains in the adhesive layer are 1.8% just prior to the crack initiation. The peel strain is much lower; between 0.15-0.2% and 0.5% axial strain in the right hand adherend.

Failure does not occur straight away, with increasing load taken by the joint and the crack growing up to a length of 0.4 mm at 4.5 kN. Shortly after exceeding 4.5 kN a critical crack length is reached and the crack grows rapidly leading to the final failure of the joint. The evolution of the crack from stable to unstable behaviour is aided by high peel and shear strains which form ahead of the crack tip. These high strains generate micro cracks ahead of the crack tip in the adhesive layer. Above 4.5 kN these micro cracks coalesce, forming a large single crack, rapidly increasing the crack growth speed, up to a maximum crack length of 3.2 mm as shown in Fig 4b) after which joint failure occurs.

Figure 2: Strain fields around the discontinuity at 2.7 kN a) Axial (ϵ_y) b) Shear (γ_{xy}) c) Peel (ϵ_x)

Figure 3: Strain fields around the discontinuity at 3.1 kN a) Axial (ϵ_y) b) Shear (γ_{xy}) c) Peel (ϵ_x)

Figure 4: Images of crack initiation and growth a) Formation of micro cracks formed ahead of crack tip at 3.8kN b) Coalescence of micro cracks at 4.5 kN into single crack (unsteady crack growth)

4 HIGH STRAIN RATE ANALYSIS

An Instron VHS 80/20 servo hydraulic test machine fitted with a 'slack adapter' system [19], capable of actuator displacement speeds up to 20 m/s is utilized in the present work. The geometry of the specimens used in this machine are of similar size as those used in section 3. The load is measured using a 100 kN Kistler piezo-electric load cell sampled at 3 MHz. A TTL pulse generator is used to synchronise the data and image capture between the test machine and the Photron SA5 high speed camera during the

failure event, triggered from the displacement of the slack adapter system just prior to engaging the loading mechanism.

Fig 5 shows the load trace from 4 specimens tested in the Instron VHS machine with an actuator velocity of 2.5 m/s. The joints load steadily up to approximately 6 kN, above which there are small fluctuations in the load trace associated with the growth of damage up to final failure at approximately 9.8 kN. The failure load during the quasi-static analysis was 4.5 kN, showing a 100% increase in the failure load of the joints due to the increased loading rate

Figure 5: Joint loading curves at 2.5 m/s

Figure 6: Specimen failure surfaces at a) 2 mm/min b) 2.5 m/s

A noticeable change in the failure surfaces for the joint is observed between the two different loading regimes. At the quasi-static rate the failure surface shows the crack growth to occur along the interface between the adhesive and the composite adherend, with practically no crack growth into the composite adherend, as shown in Fig 6a). At the elevated loading rate a different failure surface is observed, see Fig 6b), which shows fibre-tear failure between adherends. This indicates that the crack has grown within the adherend rather than just at the adhesive interface, resulting in the failure surface observed. The consistent and dramatic change in the failure surfaces at the high loading rate suggests a change in the behaviour associated with the increase in ultimate joint strength through greater interaction between the CSM face sheet and the crack front. This crack/fibre interaction is apparent from the variation in the

load traces of the four specimens in Fig 5 above 5.2 kN, indicating the variable development of damage within the joint.

The high speed loading of the joint was recorded using a Photron SA5 camera with a temporal resolution of 25 kHz. A Sigma 105mm lens was used to image an area of interest measuring 32 x 23.9mm with an image resolution of 600 x 448 pixels.. The failure of the joint occurs rapidly, approximately 1 millisecond, presenting a significant challenge in observing the development of the strain fields and damage within the joint up to failure, as very few images are recorded during the loading and failure event. Fig 7 shows the recorded failure sequence of the joint.

Figure 7: Extracts of high speed joint failure sequence at a) 2.7kN b) 3.3kN c) 4.5kN, d) 6.1kN e) 7.2kN f) 8.4kN g) 9.2kN

Analysis of the developing strain fields using DIC was first conducted with an area of interest covering the whole of the joint. Analysis The high speed images were processed with a subset size of 49 x 49 pixels and a step size of 15 pixels, producing a spatial resolution of 1.4 data points / mm. Although the spatial resolution of the data is relatively low, the analysis identifies many of the same localized axial, peel and shear strain locations around the discontinuity as shown in Fig 8. These features are very similar to those observed in previous studies of single lap joints under quasi static loading [19]. The load transfer path between the adherends can be clearly identified around the adhesive layer and adherend interfaces, Above 4.5 kN cracks are observed to grow from both discontinuities towards the center of the joint. As the load increases, the crack length extends, and an increased rotation of the joint is witnessed. A corresponding increase in the strains across the central region is also seen as the load transfer area between adherends decreases.

Figure 8: Axial (ϵ_y), Peel (ϵ_x) and Shear (γ_{xy}) strain distribution in joint a) 3.4kN, b) 6.1kN c) 8.4kN

To investigate if these localized strain features around the discontinuity differ between quasi static and high speed loading events an area measuring 12 mm x 8.9 mm around the root of the discontinuity was imaged. Magnifying optics were used to produce an image resolution of 50 pixels/mm. Analysis generated using the same correlation settings as above, delivering a spatial resolution of 3.3 data points / mm.

Inspection of the high speed image sequence given in Fig 9 shows damage to occur at the interface between the left hand adherend and the adhesive layer at the root of the discontinuity, the same location in the joint as observed in the quasi-static analysis using the high speed camera. The initial damage occurs very quickly, appearing in less than 1/25000th of a second between two images at 4.7 kN and 5.2 kN, which is twice the load of that in the quasi-static tests.

Figure 9 Extracts of the failure sequence at (a) 3.1kN – crack initiation (b) 7.6kN – damage growth at interface (c) 9.7kN – longitudinal cracking in the 90° material prior to final failure

Fig 10 shows the strain fields within the joint loaded from 4.7 kN, prior to any visual indication of damage in the joint, up to 9.7 kN just before the final joint failure. Prior to the initiation of damage in the joint, at approximately 50% of the failure load, the shear and axial strains next to the discontinuity are very similar to those in section 3 at 50% of the quasi static failure load, see Fig 10a). At the root of the discontinuity the shear and axial strains reach a maximum of 1.1%, and 0.35% respectively at the interface between the adhesive layer and the right hand adherend. Very small peel strains, with a low signal to noise ratio are observed, due to the low spatial resolution of the image, resulting in a poor correlation of the through-thickness strains, limiting the analysis of the damage initiation event. The similarity of the strains prior to damage at quasi-static and high speed loading shows that the initiation of damage is predominantly a strain critical response within brittle epoxy matrix of the right hand adherend at the root of the discontinuity, where the geometric discontinuity is the most severe, and the stress is concentrated locally in the adherend. As the load increases, and the crack begins to open, changes to the strain fields can be observed Fig 10b) and c), identifying the contribution of the left hand adherend peeling away from the joint as the restraint is removed, facilitating further crack opening. The plots also show the continued load transfer across the adhesive ahead of the crack tip, and increased strains due to the reduction in the area of load transfer between adherends.

The strain fields at 9.7 kN show high axial strain in the left hand adherend during the propagation of damage within the joint. Axial strain up to 0.65% forms within the undamaged CSM material in the right hand adherend. Transverse cracking of the epoxy matrix is also visible in the 90° fibres in the middle of the adherend due to the high axial strain in the adherend, Fig 10d), as also shown in Fig 9c). The axial strains in the CSM material identifies the continued load transfer between adherends in the damaged condition provided by fibre bridging of the CSM layers across the crack front between adherends. This is supported by the observation of the failure surfaces, which show fibres pulled out of the adherend aligned parallel to the direction of load. The CSM material also appears to provide some crack blunting properties, reducing the propagation speed in the joint, as identified by the large increase in ultimate strength compared to the results in literature discussed earlier.

Figure 10: Axial (ϵ_y), Shear (γ_{xy}) and Peel (ϵ_x) strain distribution in joint a) 4.7kN, b) 5.2kN c) 6.9kN d) 9.7kN

Although limited in resolution due to the currently available hardware, important results have been obtained. A large strengthening effect was observed due to the response of the CSM face sheet material. The initiation of damage did not form in the area of greatest peel and shear strains, but instead was observed within the adherend at the root of the discontinuity, where the geometric discontinuity is the most severe and the stress most concentrated. The complexity of the behaviour identified within the relatively simple single lap joint, demonstrates that the local strain distributions have an important, and often inter-dependent, contribution to the joint strength.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Digital Image Correlation was used to establish the component strain distributions within a composite single lap joint tested up to failure. Analysis focused on the root of the discontinuity between adherends where failure initiation is observed. The joint was tested quasi-statically and at high rate. High speed imaging was used to analyse the developing strains fields associated with damage initiation and growth with a high temporal resolution. Significant residual strength is observed after the initial development of a crack at the root of the discontinuity in the joint at 50% of the final failure load for both load cases. The strains evaluated prior to failure around the geometric discontinuity were very similar for both conditions, identifying the damage initiation to be strain critical at the discontinuity

Significant damage tolerance was demonstrated after the initial development of failure at approximately 50% of the failure load of the joint, and a 100% increase in the ultimate strength of the joint was experienced at high strain rate loading. The increases in joint strength between adherends in the matrix dominated loading direction indicate possible viscoelastic strengthening of the epoxy matrix at high strain rate. The behaviour of the CSM face sheet material was seen to have a strongly beneficial effect on the strength of the joint, altering the failure surfaces and indicating interaction between the fibres and the crack front, slowing the crack propagation.

The results show that DIC is a powerful analytical tool for the evaluation of structures under dynamic loading scenarios. This is particularly useful for complex composite structures where full knowledge of the material response and loading conditions are not known, leading to inaccurate numerical models and over engineered or inefficient structural design.

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